

ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES AND CONTRIBUTING FACTORS IN SOUTH GUJARAT: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS

Aneri K. Tankiwala¹, K.L. Chaudhary² and R.M. Naik³

1. Senior Research Fellow, Directorate of Extension Education, NAU, Navsari-396450

2. Assistant Professor, Department of Extension Education, NAU, Navsari-396450

3. Principal & Dean, N. M. College of Agriculture, NAU, Navsari-396450

anertankiwala@gmail.com

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Abstract

Environmental degradation is the major issue confronting agriculture today. Environmental impacts of agriculture and vice versa have raised serious questions about the sustainability of agricultural production systems because of widespread deterioration of soil, water, bio-diversity and air quality. These are likely to threaten the food security and livelihoods of millions of people in India. A total of 37 environmental issues were documented in South Gujarat as part of this study, categorized under climate, soil, water, biodiversity, cultural, and crop-related issues. The Garrett ranking technique was used to identify the key contributing factors. Emission from factories, air pollutants, deforestation and increased felling of tree were ranked first as a major factor for various climatic issues. Indiscriminate use of fertilizers and pesticides, loss of organic matter, heavy rainfall and loss of soil nutrients were ranked first as important factors for soil related issues. Poor recharge mechanism, disorganized state of urban water distribution system, excess application of synthetic chemicals contaminate ground water, human settlement and water salinity were ranked first as a major factor for various water related issues. Clearing forest, faster urbanization, reduction in native forest area and ornamental purpose were ranked first as important factors for bio-diversity related issues. Climatic change, introduction of high-tech practices and more incidences of pest and disease were ranked first as major factors for crop production related issues. Climate change, changing the attitude of people and introduction of modern utensils were ranked first as important factors for cultural change.

Key word: Environmental issues, Contributing factors, Garret rank, Climate change, sustainable practices, livelihood

Introduction

Environmental degradation is the major issue confronting agriculture today. Environmental impacts of agriculture and vice versa have raised serious questions about the sustainability of agricultural production systems because of widespread deterioration of soil, water, bio-diversity and air quality. In regions like South Gujarat, these issues are shaped by various natural and anthropogenic factors that contribute to environmental degradation. Understanding the specific environmental challenges and the factors responsible for them is essential for formulating effective conservation strategies and promoting sustainable practices.

This study aims to document the environmental issues affecting the South Gujarat ecosystem and identify the key factors responsible for their occurrence. This research seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the challenges facing the region. The findings will contribute to raising awareness and guiding interventions for the protection and sustainable management of the environment.

Objective

- To document the different environmental issues affecting the South Gujarat ecosystem
- To enumerate the factor responsible for prevailing environmental issues

Methodology

The environmental issues affecting the South Gujarat eco-system were documented by having elaborate discussion and interactive meeting with environmentalists, subject matter specialist and scientists of KVK, local residents and social workers. There were totally 37 environmental issues documented under this study. The documented

environmental issues were categorized under six sub headings and are given in table 1.

A schedule was prepared to enumerate the factor responsible for various environmental issues, including climate, soil, water, biodiversity, crop production, and cultural changes, along with their responsible factors. To expedite responses, the schedule was sent online via Google Forms and offline through hardcopies to experts from Navsari Agricultural University. Out of 70 judges, 60 responded. After excluding 10 incomplete or misunderstood responses, 50 valid responses were selected for further analysis.

To measure the important order of factors, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 scores were assigned for rank 1, rank 2, rank 3, rank 4, rank 5 and rank 6 respectively. To find out the most influential factors, Garrett ranking technique was employed (Garrett, 1979). As per this method, respondents were asked to allocate the rank for all factors and the outcomes of such ranking were converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Percent position} = 100 * (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$$

Where,

R_{ij}= Rank given for ith variable by jth respondents.

N_j= Number of the variable ranked by jth respondents.

With the help of Garrett Table, the percent position estimated was converted into scores. Then for each factor, the scores of each individual were added and total mean values of scores were calculated. The factors having the highest mean value was considered as the most important factor.

Result and Discussion

Table 1: Different environmental issues affecting the South Gujarat eco-system

Sr.	Environmental issues
A.	Climatic issues
1.	Variation in rainfall
1	Late onset of rainfall
2	Unseasonal rainfall
3	High intensity of rainfall
4	Uneven distribution of rainfall
5	Decreasing in number of rainy day
2.	Variation in temperature
1	Increasing temperature
2	Extreme high temperature
3.	Variation in relative humidity
1	Unfavourable high relative humidity
2	Unfavourable low relative humidity

4.	Change in wind speed/velocity
1	Undesirable high wind velocity
2	Undesirable low wind velocity
B.	Soil related issues
1	Loss of soil fertility
2	Loss of soil beneficial microbial activity
3	Subsoil compactness
4	Soil erosion
5	Soil became unsuitable for profitable crop
C.	Water related issues
1	Depletion of ground water
2	Water logging and poor drainage
3	Change in the taste of water
4	Degradation/ loss of natural surface water storage structures
5	Ground water becomes unsuitable for irrigation purpose
6	Shortage of irrigation water/ quality drinking water
D.	Biodiversity related issues
1	Prevalence of more mananimal conflict
2	Fast rate of deforestation
3	Endemic species of animal/bird are becoming endangered
4	Reduction and disappearance of plants
5	Spread of exotic or invasive plant and tress species
E.	Crop production related issues
1	More incidence - Outbreak of particular pest/disease and pest and disease developed resistance
2	Disappearance of traditional agricultural practices
3	Shift in cropping pattern
4	Lower crop yield
5	Higher weed intensity
F.	Cultural change and health related issues
1	Change in regular food habit
2	Change in dressing pattern
3	Change in the celebration of family festivals/ceremonies
4	Change in housing pattern
5.	Increase the health issues

The environmental issues affecting South Gujarat eco-system were mainly climatic issues, soil related issues, water related issues, bio-diversity related issues, crop production related issues and cultural change. Below table indicate the factors responsible for various environmental issues.

Table 02: Climatic issues and contributing factors

Sr. No.	Climatic issues and contributing factors	Garrett Score	Total mean score	Rank
A.	Variation in rainfall			
1	Deforestation	3407	68.14	1
2	Increasing green house gas emission	3281	65.62	2
3	Decreasing natural vegetation	3157	63.14	3
4	Land use change	2635	52.70	5
5	Change wind movement	2797	55.94	4
6	Invasive of exotic plants species	1578	31.56	6
B.	Variation in temperature			
1	Emission from factories	3578	71.56	1
2	Fast urbanization	3550	71.00	2
3	Deforestation	3510	70.20	3
4	Carbon dioxide emission	3299	65.98	4
5	Decreasing of amount of vegetation	3289	65.78	5
6	Inappropriate burning practices	3069	61.38	6
C.	Variation in relative humidity			
1	Air pollutants	3428	68.56	1
2	Erratic distribution of local rainfall	3246	64.92	2
3	Rise in local temperature	2865	63.76	3
4	Stubble burning	3188	57.30	4
5	Mismanagement of natural resources	1845	36.90	5
D.	Change in wind velocity			
1	Increased felling of trees	2610	52.20	1
2	Erratic changes in atmospheric temperature	2070	41.40	2

Table 03: Soil related issues and contributing factors

Sr. No.	Soil related issues and contributing factors	Garrett Score	Total mean score	Rank
A.	Loss of soil fertility			
1	Indiscriminate use of fertilizers and pesticides	3120	62.40	1
2	Soil erosion	3093	61.86	2
3	Intensive cropping	2646	52.92	3
4	Monocropping	2535	50.70	4
5	Soil transportation	1735	34.70	5
B.	Loss of soil beneficial microbial activity			
1	Loss of soil organic matter	3123	62.46	1
2	Repeated application of plant protection chemicals and synthetic fertilizers beyond the recommended level	3015	60.30	2
C.	Subsoil compactness			
1	More vehicle movement	2500	50.00	1
2	Reduced tillage operation	2454	49.08	2
3	Indiscriminate use of synthetic chemicals	2422	48.44	3
4	Soil transportation	2286	45.72	4
D.	Soil erosion			
1	Heavy rainfall	3494	69.88	1
3	Loss of natural vegetation	3474	69.48	2
2	Land resettlement	3317	66.34	3
4	Shifting cultivation	2361	47.22	4
5	Increased wind speed	2110	42.20	5
E.	Soil became unsuitable for profitable crop			
1	Loss of soil nutrients	2834	56.68	1
2	Soil salinity	2829	55.32	2
3	Disturbance in healthy soil biological process	2706	54.12	3
4	Soil contamination due to chemical inputs	2210	44.20	4
5	Mono cropping	1874	37.48	5

Table 04: Water related issues and contributing factors

Sr. No.	Water related issues contributing factors	Garrett Score	Total mean score	Rank
A.	Depletion of ground water			
1	Poor recharge mechanism	3514	70.28	1
2	Excessive use of groundwater	3444	68.88	2
3	Excessive irrigation	2670	53.40	3
4	Scanty rainfall	2320	46.40	4
5	Cultivation of exotic tree which tap more water	1700	34.00	5
B.	Water longing and poor drainage			
1	Disorganized state of urban water distribution system	2420	48.40	1
2	Shortfall in basic services like proper waste disposal	2360	47.20	2
3	Subsoil compactness	2270	45.40	3
4	Loss of natural vegetation	1582	31.64	4
C.	Change in the taste of water			
1	Excess application of synthetic chemicals contaminate ground water	2274	45.48	1
2	Effluents from industries	2216	44.32	2
3	Poor recharge mechanism	2050	41.00	3
4	Runoff from agricultural lands mixing with the local surface water reserve	1696	33.92	4
D.	Degradation/ loss of natural surface water storage structures			
1	Human settlement	3165	63.30	1
2	Conversion into residential plots	2728	54.56	2
3	Construction of tourism and recreational activities	2025	40.50	3
E.	Ground water becomes unsuitable for irrigation purpose			
1	Water salinity	2570	51.40	1
2	Sea Water ingress	2566	51.32	2
3	Industrial pollution	2376	47.52	3
4	Mismanagement of natural resources	1554	31.08	4

F	Shortage of irrigation water/ quality drinking water			
1	Poor recharge mechanism	3462	69.24	1
2	Degradation of natural surface water storage structures	2190	43.80	2
3	Industrial effluents	2055	41.10	3
4	Excessive use of chemical inputs for crop cultivation	1953	39.06	4
5	Low rainfall	1815	36.30	5

Table 05: Bio-diversity related issues and contributing factors

Sr. No.	Biodiversity related issues contributing factors	Garrett Score	Total mean score	Rank
A	Prevalence of more man-animal conflict			
1	Clearing forest	3446	68.92	1
2	Decreasing natural habitant	3384	67.68	2
3	Shortage of natural grazing	3368	67.36	3
4	Spread of exotic trees and weeds	2076	41.52	4
B.	Fast rate of deforestation			
1	Faster urbanization	3562	71.24	1
2	Human settlement	3476	69.52	2
3	Industrial purpose	3382	67.64	3
4	Conversion of forest land into agricultural land	2595	51.90	4
5	Forest fire	2428	48.56	5
6	Overgrazing of forest	2245	44.90	6
C.	Endemic species of animal/bird are becoming endangered			
1	Reduction in native forest area	2974	59.48	1
2	Climatic change	2880	57.60	2
3	Disruption in food chain	2838	56.76	3
4	Poaching animal	2590	51.80	4
D.	Reduction and disappearance of plants			
1	Clearing forest habitant	2864	57.28	1
2	Climatic change	2545	50.90	2
3	Unplanned land management activities	2540	50.80	3
4	Clearing of land for extensive cultivation	2499	49.98	4
5	Introduction of exotics	1725	34.50	5
E.	Spared of exotic or invasive plant and tress species			
1	Ornamental purpose	2595	51.90	1
2	Fuel wood requirement	2253	45.06	2
3	Domestication of market oriented exotic plants and tree species	1930	38.60	3

Table 06: Crop production related issues and contributing factors

Sr. No.	Crop production related issues contributing factors	Garrett Score	Total mean score	Rank
A	More incidence - Outbreak of particular pest/disease and			
1	Climatic change	3070	61.40	1
2	Excessive/repeated use of pesticide	2975	59.50	2
3	Monocropping	2880	57.60	3
B.	Disappearance of traditional agricultural practices			
1	Introduction of high-tech practices	2747	54.94	1
2	Unpredictable weather	2510	51.00	2
3	High-cost labour	2500	50.00	3
C.	Shift in cropping pattern			
1	Change in weather patterns	2937	58.74	1
2	Change in consumers preference	2519	50.38	2
3	Change in market demands	2576	51.52	3
D.	Lower crop yield			
1	More incidence of pest and disease	3264	65.28	1
2	Climate change	3329	66.58	2
3	Indiscriminate use of fertilizer	2438	48.76	3
4	Loss of soil nutrients	2336	46.72	4
5	Monocropping	1558	31.16	5
E.	Higher weed intensity			
1	Climate change	2832	56.64	1

2	More application of high energy synthetic inputs	2066	41.32	2
3	Introduction of exotics	512	10.24	3
F.	Disappearance of subsistence farming			
1	Climate change	2502	50.04	1
2	Domestication of market oriented commercial crops	2475	49.5	2

Table 07: Cultural change and health related issues and contributing factors

Sr. No.	Cultural change and contributing factors	Garrett Score	Total mean score	Rank
A	Change in regular food habit			
1	Climate change	2747	54.94	1
2	Habitat destruction	2519	50.38	2
3	Introduction of exotic vegetables and fruits	2367	47.34	3
B.	Change in dressing pattern			
1	Climate change	2502	50.04	1
2	Change the attitude of people	2475	49.50	2
C.	Change in the celebration of family festivals/ceremonies			
1	Change in attitude of people	2842	56.84	1
2	The disappearance of local crops/varieties	2595	51.90	2
3	The disappearance of endemic plants	2443	48.86	3
D.	Change in housing pattern			
1	Change in people attitude	2937	58.74	1
2	Change in environment	2766	55.32	2
3	Non availability of local materials	2291	45.82	3
E.	Change in traditional utensils			
1	Introduction of modern utensils	3110	62.20	1
2	Change in people attitude	2990	59.80	2
3	Non availability of local material	2614	52.28	4
4	Change in food habit	2862	57.24	3
F.	Increase the health issues			
1	Erratic weather pattern	2502	50.04	1
2	Environmental pollution	2475	49.50	2

Conclusion

This study identifies a comprehensive set of environmental challenges across several key areas, including climate, soil, water, biodiversity, crop production, and cultural change. The research highlights the critical role of industrial emissions, air pollutants, and deforestation in exacerbating climatic issues, while also emphasizing the detrimental impacts of over-reliance on fertilizers and pesticides on soil health. Water-related concerns are primarily driven by poor recharge systems, contamination from synthetic chemicals, and urban water management challenges. Biodiversity loss is largely attributed to deforestation, urban expansion, and the reduction of native forests, while crop production faces significant threats from climate change, pest outbreaks, and the adoption of high-tech agricultural practices. Finally, the study underscores the influence of climate change and shifting societal attitudes on cultural transformations.

Addressing these interconnected environmental issues requires a holistic and multi-faceted approach, integrating sustainable practices, improved resource management, and a deeper understanding of the relationship between human activities and the natural world.

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